

SOMATISMS AS A SOURCE OF METAPHOR**Umarjonova Guzal Mukhtorovna**

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Metaphor is one of the most widespread means of enriching the lexical and phraseological resources of a language and, due to its ability to participate in processes of secondary and indirect nomination, it performs a nominative function within the linguistic system. Taking into account that concepts are objectified through linguistic signs at different levels of language—such as lexical change, phraseological units, and proverbs—it is natural to assume that some phraseological units activating the concept of *hand* are metaphorical in nature.

Within the framework of cognitive theory, a conceptual metaphor (CM) is identified as the result of establishing similarities between conceptual domains that do not possess formal logical correlation in the process of constructing the meaning of speech acts. Conceptual metaphor-based formations (CMFs) are differentiated at various levels and arise as a consequence of the interaction between different knowledge structures of concepts, such as frames or scenarios.

In contrast to the views of proponents of the generative model of language (V. Weinreich, J. Katz, B. Fraser), who argue that the meanings of fixed expressions are acquired solely through their conventional usage, R. Gibbs maintains a different position. According to him, “the meanings of many phraseological units can be understood on the basis of their underlying metaphors”. The results of psycholinguistic experiments conducted by the scholar demonstrate that the meanings of many phraseological units are closely connected with conceptual structures (conceptual knowledge) within the speakers’ mental space, and that the internal form of many phraseological units is grounded in conceptual metaphors.

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ABSTRACT

Metaphor is one of the most widespread means of enriching the lexical and phraseological resources of a language and, due to its ability to participate in processes of secondary and indirect nomination, it performs a nominative function within the linguistic system

figurative meaning. The comprehension of phraseological units is thus based on the unconscious perception of conceptual metaphor-based formations and their projection onto the internal form of the unit. According to R. Gibbs, native speakers abandon the search for such a connection only in cases where literal interpretation is entirely untenable—that is, when the fixed expression contains lexical elements whose meanings are obscure and cannot be associated with any fragment of reality .

Metaphor constitutes a universal phenomenon and represents one of the most significant components of the lexical system of any language. It also serves as a link between scientific and everyday discourse. Despite the structural organization and inherent tendency toward indeterminacy within terminological systems, metaphor emerges as a natural product of language development.

The process of metaphor creation is based on an individual's cognitive ability to identify similarities and differences between objects, a capacity that plays a crucial role in human thinking. Owing to the specific characteristics of human cognition and memory, metaphorical expressions tend to be retained more effectively in memory.

Metaphor is grounded in comparison and analogy. At the same time, it reflects the semantic duality inherent in metaphor, which presupposes the participation of at least two entities—the primary (target) and the secondary (source)—within the mechanism of metaphorization. The use of metaphors facilitates the comprehension of abstract concepts and highly complex situations.

Metaphors are distinguished by imagery and expressiveness, whereas terms are characterized by precision and conciseness. However, in the process of term formation, the expressive component of meaning is typically neutralized, although a residual figurative component, displaced to the periphery of the lexical meaning, may still be preserved.

The metaphors under consideration are capable of generating new concepts on the basis of already established ones for the purpose of acquiring new knowledge; therefore, they are cognitive or conceptual in nature.

Within language, somatisms function as one of the most productive sources of metaphorization. These include lexical units denoting parts of the human body (such as *hand*, *foot*, *head*, etc.). For instance, the *foot* is an anatomical organ that enables a human being to stand upright; similarly, when we refer to the *leg of a chair*, the metaphor is motivated by the same functional principle. Likewise, *the eye of a person* corresponds metaphorically to *the eye of a window* (both serving the function of seeing), and *the wing of a bird* corresponds to *the wing of an airplane* (both enabling flight).

The breadth of connections between somatisms and phenomena of the surrounding reality is explained, first and foremost, by the ontogenetic functional characteristics of human body parts, which are easily transferred to the world of objects. It is precisely within somatisms that the process of forming secondary lexical-semantic variants becomes clearly observable, as their meanings are directly linked to human activity.

Most somatisms are integrated into polysemantic structures characterized by diverse motivational features and are associated with a large number of conceptual-figurative bases (CFBs) that form multiple semantic centers. Thus, the study of metaphors contributes to revealing the general directions in the development of metaphorical meanings. Observations

concerning the relationship between language and culture, as well as the national and cultural specificity of semantics, make it possible to identify typological features shaped through figurative means, including the distinctive characteristics inherent to a particular language.

In contemporary linguistics, special attention is paid to the value of metaphor and the factors influencing its formation. Classical linguistic studies proposed theories that revealed the core essence of metaphor; however, in most cases, metaphor was examined in isolation from context, primarily through examples of individual words or sentences. In recent years, the study of metaphor has increasingly been conducted within the framework of anthropocentric principles. An analysis of existing research indicates that modern linguistics focuses predominantly on the cognitive aspects of metaphor.

Consequently, the logical nature of metaphors—formed on the basis of long-term human experience, cultural values, geographical environment, and historical background—contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of this phenomenon. While metaphors serve to enhance the expressiveness and persuasive power of speech, they may also pose certain difficulties for foreign language learners and professionals engaged in translation practice. Metaphors whose usage spans various domains embody distinct conceptual features in each specific field.

Metaphor is a complex phenomenon, and its analysis has been ongoing for a considerable period of time. Contemporary research continues to explore metaphor theory, developing new approaches grounded in existing knowledge across various linguistic domains. Numerous definitions of this phenomenon have been proposed. In the present study, metaphor is interpreted as a cognitive mechanism that involves describing a class of objects by drawing on concepts from other domains, based on perceived similarities between the compared notions.